

ISic4282

I.Sicily inscription 4282

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini (1921) 'nel fondo
Fiorentino in contrada Portinenti'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334883

1. D (is) □ [M (anibus)]
2. Nearchia [e — — —]
3. CHEDONI □ T (itus) □ [(nomen)]
4. Polyclet [us — — —]
5. b (ene) □ m (erenti) .
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334883

Bibliography

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